

SUSTAGRI4.0: NEEDS ANALYSIS OF TRAINING IN SUSTAINABILITY, DIGITALISATION AND ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN THE AGRI-FOOD SECTOR AT VET LEVEL

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Abstract

The SUSTAGRI4.0 project “Digital marketing to promote sustainability in the agri-food industry”, is promoted by the European Commission through Erasmus+ Programme (2021-2-IE01-KA220-VET-000049494) and its core aim is to promote more sustainable agriculture and support sustainable agriculture businesses in their transition to Agriculture 4.0. This partnership for cooperation and exchanges of practices purposes to supporting local producers and sustainable agricultural business owners in the take-up of the twin transition (green and digital) for their business, through a tailored learning path combining digital skills, marketing skills and storytelling techniques. Sustagri4.0 intends to strengthen key skills in initial and continuing Vocational Education and Training (VET), by creating future-oriented curricula that better meet the needs of individuals, enabling them to be a true agent of positive change as the first step towards a deeper digitalisation and sustainability-oriented mindset of their businesses. This contribution highlights the results of the needs analysis, which is essential to understand the needs of current and future farmers, and further conform adequate training pathways and resources. In particular, results of multi-perspective research on best practices to get inspired by novel and updated experiences, along with the conduction of focus groups are reported, built on the cornerstones of sustainability, digitalization, and entrepreneurship.

Keywords: Agriculture 4.0, digital skills, marketing, sustainability.

1 INTRODUCTION

Digital marketing has transformed how companies communicate with their customers around the world. While the big brands have large communication departments that are responsible for the design and implementation of large marketing campaigns that hit the mark and attract consumers of all kinds, from the most sustainable to those attracted just by the product packaging, local producers and sustainable business are struggling to keep up with the times and their market share is shrinking year by year.

The lack of digital communication skills is typical of rural areas, characterised by weak technological infrastructure, high costs of technology, and low levels of literacy, local producers face an increasing lack of information and communication technologies (ICT) knowledge, preventing the transition of their business to Agriculture 4.0. They may have never studied farming in school or learned how to earn more money by marketing their products in a better and more sustainable way.

New tools, approaches and technologies are thus necessary so that it is easier for them to connect with customers, create a sense of community and promote a more sustainable food culture, as well as sustainability in general, while at the same time promoting their products and regaining access to a niche market that was closed to them.

SUSTAGRI4.0 core aim is to promote more sustainable agriculture and support sustainable agriculture businesses in their transition to Agriculture 4.0 [1]–[3]. Both the European Green Deal [4] and the new EU Common Agricultural Policy [5] strive to achieve sustainability at a social, environmental and economic level and set different goals, among which support for the digital transition in agriculture is a key piece. SUSTAGRI4.0 aims at supporting local producers and sustainable agricultural business owners in the take-up of the twin transition (green and digital) for their business, through a tailored learning path combining digital skills, marketing skills and storytelling techniques by developing the target groups' skills on digital marketing for sustainable agriculture.

As schematised in Fig. 1, the project partnership is formed by (i) F6S, a European based entity that has become the largest Startup/SME community globally with over 1.5 million Startups/SMEs and 2.0 million entrepreneurs; (ii) Mine Vaganti NGO, which is a non-profit organisation whose services encompass education and training, project design and development, thematic research, international mobility, and consultancy for youth and adults in the education sector; (iii) Quality Culture, a company that supports social inclusion and the green and digital transition in Europe by empowering people, especially youth, through training in quality assurance, entrepreneurship and European project management; (iv) the University of València, an international educational institution, represented by the Teaching Innovation Group in Chemical Engineering and Environment ; and (v) iAgroCert, a non-profit organisation aiming to promote agriculture and high-quality food products by enhancing brand identity and commercial value.

Figure 1. Partnership of SUSTAGRI4.0 project.

Altogether, SUSTAGRI4.0 intends to strengthen key competencies in initial and continuing vocational education and training (VET), by creating future-oriented curricula that better meet the needs of individuals, enabling them to be a true agent of positive change and creating a more favourable mindset towards digital tools and techniques as the first step towards a deeper digitalisation of their businesses. A proper needs analysis is therefore essential to understand the needs of current and future farmers, and further conform adequate training pathways and resources.

2 METHODOLOGY

Multi-perspective research was performed, considering three methodological approaches: (i) revision of best practices, to get inspired by the novel and updated experiences; (ii) conduction of a digital survey, to gather tangible and real feedback from the sector and (iii) development of focus groups with current and future professionals in the agri-food area.

The digital survey was available in the different national languages of the project partners, was implemented in the Google Forms platform, and shared through a broad social media campaign using the SUSTAGRI4.0 profiles and direct e-mailing to relevant stakeholders. The digital survey can be found in Annex I.

For the focus groups, at least 2 people were in charge of conducting the research, acting as moderators and notetakers, and guiding the discussions, without influencing the answers. As for the participants, the SUSTAGRI4.0 approach was to distinguish between current and future professionals. For current professionals, associations of farmers or individual workers were addressed. When it comes to future professionals, VET students and teachers in the agri-food branch were considered. Regarding the preparation, a set of common provisions for the development of focus groups was agreed upon among the SUSTAGRI4.0 consortium, considering guidelines for the introduction, climate and motivation of lively discussions. In addition, a set of inspiring questions and activities was designed, as a guideline, focused both on Agribusiness owners and VET professionals.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Inspiration by good practices

A set of European projects has been studied, as listed in Table 1, to highlight the most relevant synergies and keys of inspiration. The approach involved the identification of objectives, and beneficiaries, description of activities and highlight of achieved results. The analysis of the study cases provided the following learning outcomes, which served as a ground for building up the training proposal of SUSTAGRI4.0, in the field of competencies for the empowerment and enhancement of digital marketing skills towards the sustainable development of agri-food professionals.

Initiatives are focused on raising the employability level of young adults from rural and remote areas and bridging the gap between the labour market needs and the lack of knowledge and competencies of youths. Moreover, it was found that most of the evaluated projects found relevant in providing personalized training to young adults, according to their needs to improve the quality of work. For this purpose, it is necessary to ensure farmers use internet tools and smartphone applications in social and business life effectively, apart from increasing knowledge and acquiring smart farming skills. Complementarily, sustainable food systems are encouraged and exploring new ways of producing and consuming are also pursued. Finally, supporting social justice assuring fair prices for producers and educating people about healthy alimentation was highlighted.

As a part of the key findings of the reference projects, connection with land should be stressed to preserve the culture and heritage of the region and to support the economic and social sustainability of farmers. Moreover, EU regulations such as the EU Green Deal and envisioning frameworks such as the Farm-to-Fork strategy [6] must be considered.

Overall, as for the inspiring outcomes, agro-entrepreneurship must be treated as a new concept, in which farmers who live in rural areas will become more active in their social life and their work. In this regard, the design of an e-learning platform for marketing & branding of agricultural products will be differentiative issues.

Table 1. Studied projects and initiatives.

<i>Project acronym</i>	<i>Project title</i>	<i>Project URL</i>
AGRISKILLS	Innovative Skills Transfer for the Development of Agricultural Entrepreneurs	http://www.agri-skills.eu/
BURREN	BurrenLife Project	http://burrenprogramme.com/
CAMARG	Clusters of innovative zero-km Agrofood Marketplaces for Growth	https://camarg.interreg-med.eu/
DIGIFARMER	Enoculture. Start of European Enology, Prefloriger European Grapes	https://proyectoenologico.wixsite.com/en/
FARMINC	Introducing Marketing & Branding Principles in the Agricultural Sector	http://farminceu.militos.org/
FUTURE FARMERS	Skills for Future Farmers	http://future-farmer.eu/
GENERATIONAG	Digital Transformation and Digital Communication for Agri-food Businesses	https://www.generationag.org/
ALVEARECHEDICESI	L'aveare che dice sì	https://alvearechedicesi.it/
ITALIAVOLA	L'ITALIA VOLA	https://italiavola.com/
RBAPS	Pilot result-based agri-environment measures in Ireland and Navarra	https://rbaps.eu/
SMART FARM	Smart Farm Training for Employment	http://sfate.eu/
URBAN CO-OP	Urban Co-op Limerick	https://www.theurbanco-op.ie/

3.2 Digital survey

After the analysis of best practices, and considering the keywords of interest in the training, an online questionnaire was designed. This questionnaire was divided into three main areas of skills: sustainability, entrepreneurship and digital business. It was designed to semi-quantitatively (Likert scale: 1-5) analyse, for each topic under the skill area, three dimensions: (i) awareness of current personal skills; (ii) interest in learning this topic; and (iii) perception of difficulty to implement this topic professionally. In addition, an open-answer question was focused on needs, barriers and strengths in these areas. Another section asked about their perception of the training profile and innovation ecosystem around the respondents. Apart from the collection of information, the questionnaire was designed to provoke curiosity and reflection about the different skills that a professional in the sector could be interested in.

The analysis of the outcomes of this experience highlighted that the impact of responses to the e-form was very limited, and no specific conclusions could be taken from this approach. It was considered that the questionnaire could be found difficult and long, which may be a barrier to getting a bigger number of responses. However, a simplified questionnaire could not offer significant and representative data to continue working on. Nonetheless, the design of the survey is considered appropriate for the second stage of the SUSTAGRI4.0 project, in combination with the future e-course. In particular, the questionnaire could be used in *ex-ante* and *ex-post* scenarios to measure the impact of the e-course towards learning and improving the skills of current and future farmers.

3.3 Focus groups

A focus group is a qualitative research method for collecting information through group discussions. Focus group planning includes determining roles, recruiting participants, and preparing to facilitate discussions. Two focus groups were conducted by every partner, as gathered in Table 2.

Table 2. Focus group description.

Partner	Focus group	City, Country
 iAgroCert	KOSMOS Agricultural cooperative	Veroia, Greece
	VET trainers from Thesaloniki and Kozani	Thesaloniki and Kozani, Greece
 F6S	Urban Co-op cooperative	Limerick, Ireland
	VET trainers	Dublin, Ireland
 MineVaganti NGO	School N. Pellegrini to VET trainers	Sassari, Italy
	School N. Pellegrini to VET students of the degree Agricultural Production and Methodologies	Sassari, Italy
 Quality Culture	Agricultural cooperative Coraggio	Rome, Italy
	VET trainers	Online focus group, Italy
 Universitat de València	VET centre IES Vicent Gandia, VET students of the degree in Agricultural and Landscaping Management	Castelló de la Ribera, Spain
	VET centre IES Josep Segrelles, VET students and trainers of the degree in Agricultural Production	Albaida, Spain

The analysis of focus groups was the most relevant source of information to understand the needs for training of the target beneficiaries of SUSTAGRI4.0. The main outcomes of the focus groups are schematized in Fig. 2 and summarized as follows.

Figure 2. Outcomes of the focus groups: from out-of-date self-perception to genuine digital business skills.

The self-perception on digital and entrepreneurship skills is different for agri-businesses owners and future farmers (i.e., VET students in the agri-food branch). It is connected with the social framework and previous training programs that the people are subjected to. Therefore, a versatile program should be designed to gain digital business skills, which are considered essential to boost robust businesses in the agri-food area. In this line, giving knowledge on sustainability together with digitalization, entrepreneurship and digital marketing skills becomes necessary.

Sustainability is a complex concept, merely understood in terms of environmental impact, connecting to resource consumption, climate change and waste management. Complementarily, a wider perspective can be therefore offered, and social sustainability has to be stressed. Moreover, to have tangible results, the value of the company/product for being sustainable should be highlighted, establishing connections with regulations at local, national and European levels. In this regard, circular economy practices can help create sustainable businesses, involving the outmost hot topics of bioeconomy, biodiversity, renewable energies, management of waste or 0 km strategies.

The main needs and interests in digitalisation skills were focused on knowledge of digital applications (software) for agricultural production and on novel technologies (hardware and Internet of Things (IoT)), which can make a difference. In this line, the benefits of the introduction of technologies in the farm should be highly stressed, to break the barriers of current farmers. For this purpose, skills in content creation (images, infographics, videos, animations) are considered essential.

In terms of entrepreneurship skills, the main needs and interests involve the consideration of more initiatives for training and the development of educational tools to support its digitalization phase. In the agricultural sector, which is mainly dominated by older people, intergenerational collaboration and transition are essential to encompass a smooth transformation. In contrast, new businesses can be built on novel digital relationships and consumption modes. A market should be available for both models. Complementary entrepreneurship skills are strategy-focused thinking canvas, which could be of relevance to settling down sustainable businesses. This could be the case of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats (SWOT), Value Proposition Canvas (VPC), Business Model Canvas (BMC) or design thinking approaches according to political, economic, social, technological, environmental, and legal external factors (PESTEL), among others. Additionally, the knowledge of basic skills of datasheets and statistics to understand the evolution and impact of the measures taken in the businesses are essential in any training program. Also, collaborative approaches and networking should be encouraged, in contrast to individual battles. Particular interest in crowdfunding platforms and strategies should be stressed.

Finally, as for digital marketing skills, it may be highlighted that those purely related to marketing are poor. Moreover, one must bear in mind that the tool does not ensure the knowledge, and the knowledge

does not ensure the impact. Therefore, a focused vision should be given. As well, farm owners are very concerned about the ability to access educational opportunities in smart agriculture and digital marketing, although they are eager to incorporate these practices into their work. In this regard, professional market-focused use of the internet and social networks should be a basic skill, with special emphasis on the benefits and strategies for advertising through the internet. The ability to create stimulating videos (both technical skills and storytelling) is outstanding to catch younger generations to their markets. Particularly, responsible digital communication and storytelling, deepening the knowledge of consumers and avoiding greenwashing, are necessary. Likewise, correct formal writing and correspondence functionalities of mail servers should be understood to get to a wider audience. All these digital tools are usually available for computers, but also the use of smartphones as an operation centre will benefit businesses, due to their decentralization of use. Therefore, the use of cloud systems and synchronous collaborative applications can be of relevance.

Altogether, concerns and requirements of a future training pathway should carefully be designed in terms of length, conciseness, and clarity. The selection of terminology must be considered with caution, to both inspire attractiveness and reduce barriers by discouragement. The program should be easily accessible and compatible with smartphones, involving micro-learning flexible lessons. Moreover, the program, whatever the key topic is highlighted, should be connected to entrepreneurship, to transmit the significance of learning for envisioning positive futures. Also, sustainability should be included in all aspects of the program, as a transversal issue.

To conclude, hybrid strategies should be considered for the success of the project. Therefore, partnering with appropriate associates such as VET centres, chambers of commerce or agri-business cooperatives could improve the reach of the training program. This could help in terms of follow-up and peer-to-peer approaches. Digital marketing should be inclusive and consider specific approaches to get to people with personal disabilities, such as deafness or dyslexia, or social disabilities. The program should directly address the potential difficulties and barriers that an individual could find, to provide arguments in favour of the investment as a positive cost/benefit approach.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The agricultural sector, which is mainly dominated by older people, needs more initiatives for training, together with the development of educational tools to support its digitalization phase. Farm owners are very concerned about the ability to access educational opportunities in smart agriculture and digital marketing, although they are eager to incorporate these practices into their work. Sustainability is more linked to environmental protection, so the farm owners link their perspective with smart farming and cultivation methods to reduce pollution. They need to be more trained on the way they could incorporate sustainability and digitalization in other phases of their work.

The combination of field (best practices) and desk research (digital survey & focus groups) stand out as innovation factors as compared with existing projects and practices. Specific tools for desk research were designed. Results on the perception of needs of current and future farmers in the fields of sustainability, digitalisation and entrepreneurship were highlighted.

The obtained results will be used for the elaboration of an educational e-course on digital marketing for sustainable agriculture businesses, covering key concepts of mentoring, digital marketing, social media and blogging. The e-course will be built upon the cross-analysis of the level of digital literacy of the target group and their knowledge of digital and social media marketing. The needs and obstacles concerning their implementation will be carefully considered, in combination with the identification of methodological shortcomings, adaptability factors and gaps concerning the specific target group and their specific needs.

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ANNEX I: DESIGN OF THE DIGITAL SURVEY

Sustainability skills

Please rate from 1 (low) to 5 (high), or 0 (don't know/unsure), your level of (i) Awareness of current personal skills; (ii) Interest in learning this topic; and (iii) Perception of difficulty to implement this topic professionally. In addition, please explain your needs, barriers and strengths in these areas.

<i>Topic</i>	<i>Awareness (1-5)</i>	<i>Interest (1-5)</i>	<i>Difficulty (1-5)</i>	<i>Id</i>
Sustainability				2.1
Environmental impact of your profession				2.2
Social impact of your profession				2.3
Economic impact of your profession				2.4
European initiatives: GreenComp – EU Framework of skills on sustainability				2.5
European initiatives: Green Deal				2.6
European initiatives: Strategy from farm to fork				2.7
European initiatives: Strategy of Circular Economy				2.8
European initiatives: Strategy of Bioeconomy				2.9
Climate change				2.10
Food and non-food by-products and co-products valorisation				2.11
Best practices in agri-food digitalisation				2.12
Soil nutrients and water management				2.13
Biodiversity				2.14
Waste management				2.15
Unforeseen skills/topics				2.16
Needs				2.17
Barriers				2.18
Strengths				2.19

Entrepreneurship skills

Please rate from 1 (low) to 5 (high), or 0 (don't know/unsure), your level of (i) Awareness of current personal skills; (ii) Interest in learning this topic; and (iii) Perception of difficulty to implement this topic professionally. In addition, please explain your needs, barriers and strengths in these areas.

<i>Topic</i>	<i>Awareness (1-5)</i>	<i>Interest (1-5)</i>	<i>Difficulty (1-5)</i>	<i>Id</i>
European initiatives: EntreComp – EU Framework of skills in entrepreneurship				3.1
Analytical techniques (e.g.SWOT or PESTEL)				3.2
Creative design thinking for business models				3.3
Diversification of businesses				3.4
Marketing strategies: metrics and insights				3.5
Collaboration and networking				3.6
Economic issues (e.g., cost/benefit analysis, ROI, funding...)				3.7
Storytelling				3.8
Pitching				3.9
Blogging				3.10
Corporative visual identity				3.11
Decision-making strategies				3.12
Planning and coordinating production				3.13
Quality management, quality assurance and quality control				3.14
Ethics for agri-food products				3.15
Unforeseen skills/topics				3.16
Needs				3.17
Barriers				3.18
Strengths				3.19

Digital business skills

Please rate from 1 (low) to 5 (high), or 0 (don't know/unsure), your level of (i) Awareness of current personal skills; (ii) Interest in learning this topic; and (iii) Perception of difficulty to implement this topic professionally. In addition, please explain your needs, barriers and strengths in these areas.

<i>Topic</i>	<i>Awareness (1-5)</i>	<i>Interest (1-5)</i>	<i>Difficulty (1-5)</i>	<i>Id</i>
European initiatives: DigComp - Framework of digital skills				4.1
Digital technologies to communicate (e.g., web, social media, newsletters, forums)				4.2
Data handling and analysis				4.3
Logistics and farm management information systems				4.4
B2C e-commerce				4.5
B2B e-commerce				4.6
Use of the Internet of Things (IoT)				4.7
Weather forecasting tools				4.8
Farming-focused apps for the smartphone				4.9
Combine online and offline promotion activities				4.10
Combine online and offline logistics activities				4.11

Unforeseen skills/topics		4.12
Needs		4.13
Barriers		4.14
Strengths		4.15

Training and innovation ecosystem

Please rate from 1 (low) to 5 (high), or N/A (don't know/unsure), your level of perception in the following items:

<i>Topic</i>	<i>Perception (1-5)</i>	<i>Id</i>
Awareness of training programs in the agri-food industry		5.1
Quality of training programs to meet challenges for professionals in the agri-food industry		5.2
Willingness to attend in-person training programs.		5.3
Willingness to attend online training programs.		5.4

Please identify 3 training providers in your professional sector, or else say "Unknown". Please include a webpage, if possible **[Id 5.5]**

- 1 Provider 1:
- 2 Provider 2:
- 3 Provider 3:

Please identify 3 examples in which technology has aided your profession, or else answer "Unknown". Please include a webpage, if possible **[Id 5.6]**

- 1 Example 1:
- 2 Example 2:
- 3 Example 3:

YOUR THOUGHTS, YOUR PERSONAL VISION, ADDITIONAL COMMENTS

Optionally, please use this free space to show your vision on the topics related to this survey, concerning your professional development and career. Your thoughts are welcome to help design proper intervention actions for training in digital skills for sustainable businesses in the agri-food sector. We warmly appreciate your contribution.